

DL-Mercapto succinic acid as metallochromic indicator for volumetric estimation of copper by sodium thiosulphate

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THE volumetric estimation of copper by thio-sulphate solution is well known. Nowadays EDTA method is widely used for determination of copper ion using indicators such as Eriochrom black-T, Murexide, Pyro catechol violet, Dithiozone, Fast sulphon black F, etc.¹.

The transitional method of estimation of copper by iodometric method using thiosulphate may be replaced by direct titration without using KI.

A solution of copper chloride was prepared by dissolving 6.06 gm $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 250 ml of distilled water. A stock solution of 1% DL-mercapto succinic acid (thiomalic acid BDH Chemical Ltd., England) was prepared dissolving 1% of the substance in 100 ml of distilled water. 0.1M sodium thiosulphate solution was prepared by dissolving 24.821 gm of pure $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (BDH Chemicals, England) in one litre distilled water.

When DL-mercapto succinic acid is added in aqueous solution containing copper ions, violet coloured precipitates are formed. The coloured precipitates are due to formation of metal indicator complex. The estimation of copper may be carried out as follows.

Take 10 ml of copper chloride solution in the conical flask. Add 4-5 drops of DL-mercapto succinic acid as an indicator. Initial colour formed by adding indicator is violet. This is titrated against the standard solution of (0.1M) thiosulphate. A sharp colour change from violet to colourless takes at the end point. The procedure was repeated several times to obtain constant reading. Amount of copper was calculated. The amount of copper obtained by this method was the same as that obtained by standard EDTA titration using Eriochrome black-T as an indicator. The end point shows the proportion of copper to thiosulphate $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ to be 1 : 1.

In the present investigation a method similar to EDTA titration was followed using metal chromic indicator.

New indicator used was DL-mercapto succinic acid

which fulfils all the requirements of metal-chromic indicators.

The stability of the complex with thiosulphate being greater than that of the metal-indicator complex the latter dissociates to a limited extent and during the titration the free metal ions are progressively complexed by $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ until the metal ion is completely displaced from metal indicator. Results show that the ratio of copper to $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ is 1 : 1 molar proportion.

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Reference

1. A. I. VOGEL, "A text book of quantitative inorganic analysis." Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., England 1961. p. 424.

Solubility products of Cu(II) and Ag(I) complexes of glycoldimercaptoacetate

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SAXENA and coworkers have made extensive study on the complexing tendencies of several thiols with various metals¹⁻⁵. This communication reports the composition of sparingly soluble complexes of Cu(II) and Ag(I) with glycoldimercaptoacetate by amperometric, pH-metric and conductometric titrations; their equilibrium constants and solubility products by polarographic technique applying Ringbom's method. The changes in the thermodynamic parameters of free energy, enthalpy, entropy accompanying the complexation reactions have also been determined at 30°.

Experimental

Glycoldimercaptoacetate (referred here as GDA) was obtained from Evan's Chemicals, New York and other chemicals were of analar grade. Freshly prepared solutions were used to avoid the effects of ageing and air oxidation. Conductance and pH were measured respectively with an electronic eye-type conductometer and Cambridge bench pH meter associated with a glass-calomel electrode assembly. A manual polarograph, with scalamp galvanometer as current recorder and S.C.E. as reference electrode, was used for amperometric titrations in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The capillary used had the following characteristics in 25% ethanol by volume, 0.1M NaClO_4 and 0.002% Triton X-100 at -0.5 V vs. S.C.E. with h_{eff} value being 38.3 cm :

$$m = 2.963 \text{ mg/sec.}, \quad t = 2.39 \text{ sec.}$$